

VARICOSE VEINS TREATMENT FOR WOMEN AT HAMPTONS

Women always want to have nice and smooth legs throughout their lives. But the varicose veins, however, made them their victim. [Varicose vein treatment Hampton](#)s provides a proper solution to this problem. It is a cosmetic concern but in some cases, it can be harmful. Some women complain that the varicose veins cause them some amount of discomfort and pain in the legs. It is always best to get them looked at **varicose vein treatment near me Hampton**s to see what type of treatment they will provide for you to get rid of this problem.

Mostly, it will not hurt you and only look bad. Some **vein treatments Hampton**s you may want to consider:

1. Radiofrequency ablation: In this type of treatment you will get a high-frequency current that brings heat to the dilated veins. This closes them after damaging the veins internally. The **vein doctor** will help, to put you to sleep, this is due to the pain caused by this treatment. After getting this treatment you have not to worry about your veins.

2. Non-surgical treatment: For non-surgical treatment, the best option is compression stockings. This will help you to relieve the aching and swelling of your legs. Stockings play a vital role in the flowing of blood that goes to the heart from the legs. But this does not guarantee the further formation of varicose veins. You have to go to **vein treatments near me** for better consultation and understanding of these stockings.

3. Surgery: Surgery is the last option for you. If you are going through severe pain and aching in your varicose veins then you should go for this option. Before opting for the surgery, you have to consider [vein doctor Hamptons](#) who will provide you much more information related to the surgery. Ligation and stripping are the two most commonly used methods in the surgery of varicose veins. In this surgery, the veins are being removed which causes you the problem.

What are the risk factors that cause varicose veins in women?

The varicose veins development in women depends on these several factors:

- During periods- During the period women go through hormonal changes. This is one of the major risk factors for women who have a varicose veins problem. The hormones of females tend to relax the vein valves at this period.
- Inactivity- Sitting and standing for a longer duration of time can also cause varicose veins in women. The inactivity prevents the blood from flowing regularly, which results in the formation of blood clots.
- Pregnancy- At the time of pregnancy, the blood flow volume increases. This will have side effects on your body by enlarging the vein's valves, but it is very beneficial for the fetus.
- Leg injury- If you are going through some serious leg injury, it may result in varicose veins. Due to the leg injury, sometimes blood clots form, which prevents blood from flowing properly.
- Aging- If you are above the age of 35, then the chances are 70% of having varicose veins. The vein valves that regulate the blood flow have been going through wear and tear at this age.